

Symmetric Operational Rules for n_{\pm} and Their Extensions

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$$1 + 2 + 3 + \dots + n = \frac{n(n+1)}{2} = n_+$$

$$2n_+ = n^2 + n = n_+ \cdot (n_+ + n_-) \dots \textcircled{1}$$

$$\sqrt{n_+} + \sqrt{n_-} = \sqrt{(\sqrt{n_+} + \sqrt{n_-})^2}$$

$$\sqrt{(\sqrt{n_+} + \sqrt{n_-})^2} = \sqrt{2 + 2\sqrt{n_+n_-}} \dots \textcircled{2}$$

$$\sqrt{n_+} - \sqrt{n_-} = \sqrt{(\sqrt{n_+} - \sqrt{n_-})^2}$$

$$\sqrt{(\sqrt{n_+} - \sqrt{n_-})^2} = \sqrt{2 - 2\sqrt{n_+n_-}} \dots \textcircled{3}$$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{n_+}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{n_-}} = \frac{\sqrt{2 + 2\sqrt{n_+n_-}}}{\sqrt{n_+n_-}} \dots \textcircled{4}$$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{n_+}} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{n_-}} = \frac{\sqrt{2 - 2\sqrt{n_+n_-}}}{\sqrt{n_+n_-}} \dots \textcircled{5}$$

Based on the study 'Restructuring and Correlation of Factorials through the Redefinition of Arithmetic Operations,' this research establishes the symmetric relationship of n_{\pm} and extends it to irrational and rational expressions.

Reference

Kim(2026). A Study on the Reconstruction and Correlation of Factorials Through the Definition of Basic Arithmetic Operations. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19960864>